

Experiential Marketing and Service Quality, And Customer Loyalty: Social Concept and Application

**Elvie Maria¹, Wan Suryani^{2*}, Lenggogeni³, Wikrama Wardana⁴,
Anthon Tondo⁵**

¹ Universitas IBBI, Medan, Indonesia.

² Universitas Medan Area. Indonesia.

³ Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional. Indonesia.

⁴ Universitas Pramita Indonesia.

⁵ Universitas Swiss German. Indonesia

Corresponding author: Wan Suryani
Universitas Medan Area. Indonesia

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Abstract

Utilizing a descriptive quantitative approach, our study investigates the effects of experiential marketing and service quality on customer loyalty. The analysis centers on the consumption patterns of Eating Abeng 38 restaurant customers as the unit of observation and unit of analysis. Our population consists of 5894 patrons in 2018, yet through the application of the Slovin technique, we appropriately sampled 98 individuals. The research's pertinent data was collated and assessed through multiple linear regression analytic techniques. When analyzed, it was discovered that customer loyalty is to some extent positively influenced by experiential marketing, as well as by service quality, which has a positive impact. Additionally, when both experiential marketing and service quality are combined, they have a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty.

Keywords: Experiential Marketing, Service Quality, Customer Loyalty.

1. Introduction

With intensified rivalry in the industry, the enterprise strives to keep its current patrons devoted, all while also aiming to attract fresh prospects. This is crucial since corporate customers generate a considerable portion of the company's income, which directly affects their long-term sustainability. For individuals who yearn for Chinese culinary delights within the confines of their own abode, "Eating Abeng 38" is the optimal choice for you. Nestled at the conclusion of Gang Bawean No. 38 in Medan, this restaurant boasts an array of scrumptious selections, including their signature dishes of Capchai, Khau Bak, Tin Chicken, and Shrimp Taucho.

Despite using Experiential Marketing, Rumah Makan Abeng 38 has garnered low ratings from clients because of limited seating, inadequate parking provisions, and poor ventilation. These factors have hindered the restaurant's ability to deliver an exceptional dining encounter for its clients, which results in unfulfilled expectations and a lack of enduring satisfaction. In turn, this lack of positive experiences may prevent customers from returning and becoming loyal patrons, as noted in Mukminin & Latifah's (2020) study.

Eating Abeng 38's services are inadequate, plagued by various issues. Most notably, patrons frequently grumble about tardy employee response times, a shortage of information relating to vegetarian options, and inadequate staffing for in-house diners. Naturally, customers become disgruntled, potentially damaging Eating Abeng 38's reputation and costing them their patronage. To avoid such losses, loyalty to a company must be established organically, not artificially forced upon the client. In essence, companies must prioritize the development of loyal customers through quality service as a means of avoiding defection to rival companies. Growing companies are typically capable of increasing customer loyalty, resulting in a reduction of competitive susceptibility. The loyalty of customers is reliant on various factors like quality of service and experiential marketing, as reported by Ameen et al. (2021). Acuan yang terpenging dari loyalitas pelanggan adalah kepercayaan pelanggan (Chu, Lee, & Chao, 2012; Stathopoulou & Balabanis, 2016)

By eliciting emotional responses and engendering positive feelings towards the products and services, experiential marketing cultivates devoted customers. Companies adopting this tactic create products or services that resonate with consumers on a sensory, emotional, and intellectual level. They tap into the emotional value of the product for an unforgettable experience resulting in customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction qualifies a company's business as repeat business. This approach is beneficial for companies, which ensures gluing customer loyalty. New business opportunities can arise when contented customers share their positive experiences with others. Marketing experiences transcend mere dissemination of fundamental information about a product or service.

Due to a reduction in the number of patrons dining in-house, a decrease in sales was discovered after the initial interview. According to Kotler & Keller (2016), if a customer is loyal, they will continue to support and purchase their preferred products and services regardless of external factors or marketing efforts to persuade them otherwise. Yusrianti¹ et al. (2017) suggest that loyalty is demonstrated through regular purchases made as a result of a thought-out decision-making process. In conclusion, Mickelsson & Lipkin (2015) characterize customer loyalty as a behavioral pattern associated with a particular brand, whereby the probability of renewing an agreement with the same brand in the future and embracing positive word-of-mouth promotion is high.

Inferred from the knowledge gathered, customer loyalty pertains to the actions exhibited by consumers in showing their dedication, trust, and advocacy towards a brand's merchandise. This

poses a great managerial obstacle as it can amplify the favorable reputation of a product. Patrons who are loyal to a specific brand are predisposed to staying devoted to it and are prone to repurchasing the same item, regardless of the numerous substitutes accessible. Consumers who believe in a company's quality may become less profitable if they fall under attack from competitors, who influence customer perception of their offerings. However, those who remain loyal can still offer invaluable insight and suggestions to improve a company's product offerings. Ultimately, they prioritize quality over price, which speaks volumes about their relationship with the brand. (Afthanorhan et al., 2019) outlines the key ingredients of customer loyalty as follows:

1) Known as generic loyalty, the concept of brand loyalty implies that consumers tend to consistently buy a particular brand.

Brand loyalty and repeat purchase are terms that are frequently used together; however, they have different meanings. Specifically, brand loyalty is an emotional connection to a particular brand, whereas repeat purchase behavior refers to the act of repeatedly buying the same brand.

(1) The success of a certain company is based on how they make their products the only option available, leading to the concept of repeat purchases. (1) Consistently utilizing marketing strategies, this company persuades and entices customers to choose their brand repeatedly. Building customer loyalty is influenced by various elements such as customer actions, frequent purchases, and general principles. For businesses to create a devoted following, they must cater to the wants, concerns, and needs of their clients. This nurturing approach will satisfy individuals, which in turn, will build a lasting relationship with the company. Recent studies indicate that businesses that prioritize customer happiness have a higher likelihood of achieving customer loyalty (Noor, 2020).

2. Experiential Marketing

The personalized experience that results from specific stimuli, as provided by marketers before and after a product or service purchase, constitutes experiential marketing, as explained by Beyond and (Mollen & Wilson, 2010). (Zulki Zulkifli Noor, 2020) delves further, defining experiential marketing as the result of a private event in response to particular stimuli provided by marketing activities both before and after purchase. By this definition, experiential marketing captures the subjective experience of a company's offerings, designed to invoke emotional and sentimental connections with the consumer.

Identifying five crucial factors for measuring experiential marketing, Zulki Zulkifli Noor in 2020 named them as follows:

Sensory experience is a sense that we all possess.

Engaging a customer's senses in the marketplace is known as Sense Experience. This technique generates business-oriented experiences that appeal to the five senses: sound, sight, touch, taste, and smell. By utilizing Sense Experience, companies can differentiate themselves and their products, inspire consumer investment, and deliver added customer value.

Experience / Feelings are key.

The leveraging of emotional stimuli, including events, objects, and agents, as part of an effective strategic approach is key to the promotion of consumer brand through multiple channels such as personnel, co-branding, product contents, website, packaging, and advertising. Enterprises must understand the power of emotional experiences in influencing purchasing decisions and driving the imagination of consumers. The goal of Feel Experience is to inspire and influence the emotions and mindset of consumers through these strategic approaches.

Experience the creativity of your mind through thinking.

Through the inventive "Think Experience" approach, the company's intention is to encourage customers to rethink their brand perception and generate a sense of creativity. The goal is to instill a strong desire for innovative, valuable, and progressive ideas by harnessing revolutionary technology and introducing unexpected elements of surprise.

Act on your physical experience to determine the lifestyle you are entitled to. Your lifestyle should reflect your unique physical abilities and needs. Don't conform to societal standards that may not align with your body and health. Instead, embrace your individuality and make choices that support your well-being. Your body is your own, so make sure your lifestyle honors it.

Through various marketing techniques, companies strive to create customer experiences that deeply resonate with their physical bodies, behavioral patterns, and lifelong interactions with others. One's interests, actions, and opinions define their lifestyle, which in turn shapes these experiences. The Experience Act can either keep up with current cultural trends or establish new ones. By utilizing this act, a company hopes to not only reflect lifestyle and behavior but also foster communal connections using meticulously crafted strategies.

Using five key factors, namely interconnection, senses, emotions, behavior, and cognition, one can analyze the effectiveness of the company's experiential marketing strategy. Such metrics can provide valuable insights when conducting research.

In today's market, competitive edge is achieved by companies that prioritize providing great experiences across all industries, as emphasized by Sanders – the Director of Yahoo – in Zarem's (2000, p.28-31) research. Exceptional flying experiences, high safety standards, and competitive pricing are ways airlines differentiate themselves and cater to customer cravings for unforgettable moments. Sanders believed that the economy has shifted into the "experience" realm. On the other hand, Lippman, the president of corporate sales and marketing for Emap USA, challenged this view, stating that marketing has been a concept since ancient times and is not a novel one. Products and services can now be marketed in various ways due to the evolution of marketing. Cable TV and the internet have provided more platforms for marketers to use. The effectiveness of the old marketing concept has not diminished; it has only been presented differently, according to Lippman. Wong (2005, p.11) also suggests that using experience can make a difference in setting products and services apart. Despite technological advancements, it can still be difficult or impossible to create distinctions between products. The competition for a product inevitably tightens as rivals offer the same features and it becomes more established, leaving slim opportunities for differentiation.

To tackle the issue at hand, Wong (2005, p.11) proposes a couple of options: Differentiation based on the quality of competition or on the methods and locations involved. The ultimate aim of marketers is to differentiate themselves in the best possible manner. This may involve enhancing operational performance and quality or adopting unique approaches to stand out from competitors. Marketers can also leverage advanced technologies to create effortless checkout experiences, empowering customers to conduct transactions as they see fit. Additionally, they can implement innovative procedures to set themselves apart from the rest. To forge a deep connection with customers, it is crucial for marketers to tap into emotional triggers and distinguishing design elements. The days of mere quality, features, and brand reputation as differentiating factors are long gone, rendering promotional tactics insufficient. What truly cements a brand in the consumer psyche are reminiscent emotions and one-of-a-kind interactions. This necessitates a multi-pronged approach that not only achieves marketing goals but also fulfills promises made. An essential element of building brand value is creating an experiential foundation that engenders powerful, lasting bonds between consumer lifestyle and product. In order to effectively promote products and services, it's necessary

for marketers to create a strong emotional connection with potential customers through associations with various lifestyles and interests within a wide social context. A combination of tactics such as public relations, sponsorship promotions, special events, and advertisements as recommended by Widdis (2001, p.18) can be employed to achieve this objective. The internet also provides an opportunity to transmit messages in a way that leaves an unforgettable impression. Another useful technique is point of sale displays that can effectively communicate these experiences. Sanders believes that experiential marketing can even be achieved through online strategies like streaming media which allows for live events, seminars, and interviews. Zarem (2000, p.28-31) points out that brand loyalty can be effectively targeted by marketers utilizing the point-of-sale. This technique, if executed correctly, can yield great results.

3. Service quality

It is widely stated by (Exposito & Sanchis-Llopis, 2018) that quality of service is a reflection of a product's overall benefits to customers. However, (Nur Fiqhi Utami & Mutiarin, 2017) argue that it's more dynamic and is impacted by a number of ever-changing factors such as individual services, procedures, people and locations that can go beyond expectations. This implies that quality of service is a complex entity that hedges on a variety of factors such as environment, persons, procedures, products and services for the ultimate satisfaction and benefit of the customer.

In 2022, Hariadi DP et al. uncovered various elements that influence service quality. The identified factors are as follows:

Manufacturers offer a valuable bundle of services for free, which contains important information such as street names and directions, usage guidelines of the product, pricing, delivery schedule, sale and service regulations, warnings, updates, documentation, reserved confirmations, account summaries, as well as receipts and tickets.

1) Management and technical consulting, auditing, private counseling, and advisory services are among the various forms of consultations available.

Order taking encompasses three crucial elements: order entry, application methods for club memberships or other programs, and reservation services. Exclusive facilities with restricted capacity, like exhibitions, professional appointments, seating arrangements, event spaces, and table arrangements are potentially included in reservation services.

In order to create a safe and comfortable haven for visitors, Hospitality offers a plethora of facilities, including but not limited to transportation and security.

Protecting a customer's bought items, which is referred to as caretaking, involves close attention and care.

Prior to product delivery, special requests must be accommodated and feedback in the form of complaints, suggestions, and compliments must be addressed as part of the customer service duties. Providing assistance for any usage difficulties and handling warranties and guarantees for malfunctions are also part of the job. Issues that arise from product failure, involving staff or customers, must be resolved. Restitution, which may involve compensation, refunds, or indemnity, may be necessary to address the complications.

1) Billing procedures must incorporate invoicing for each transaction.

2) For each transaction, invoicing must be included in the billing process.

3) Including invoicing for individual transactions is crucial for billing procedures.

4) To ensure proper billing, invoicing for every transaction should be integrated into the process.

5) It is vital to include invoicing for each transaction as part of the billing procedure.

4. Research Methods

The Abeng 38 establishment in Medan was observed for research purposes. The research timeframe spanned from May 2021 to June 2022. Utilizing Bungin's (2011) definition of quantitative descriptive research, the selected methodology is grounded in positivist principles and employed to examine a populace or particular subset. To obtain data, research apparatuses were utilized and logically evaluated via quantitative analysis or statistical examination of the pre-determined hypothesis. In 2018, Eating Abeng 38 was dined by 5894 subscribers who formed the population of this study. Research was conducted with a sample size of 98 respondents.

5. Results And Discussion

For those looking to indulge in traditional Chinese cuisine without leaving their homes, "Eating Abeng 38" is the perfect spot, featuring a variety of dishes. Nonetheless, with growing competition in the industry, it's crucial for the company to retain current customers and bring in fresh ones. The importance of this stems from the fact that enterprise clients are essential for the business's long-term survival as they provide a significant source of income. Located at Gang Bawean No. 38 in Medan, you'll find a unique restaurant that boasts an array of delicious dishes. Some of their standout menu items include the savory Khau Bak, the delectable Capchai, and the indulgent Tin Chicken and Shrimp Taucho.

At Rumah Makan Abeng 38, customers are experiencing subpar dining due to inadequate use of Experiential Marketing, leading to a consistent stream of negative feedback. Issues like insufficient ventilation, inadequate parking, and a limited seating contribute to the dissatisfaction experienced by patrons during their visits, hampering their overall dining experience. As per a study conducted by Mukminin and Latifah in 2020, this lack of lasting positive impressions has led to a decline in customer loyalty for the establishment.

Abeng 38's services fail to meet expectations in terms of providing quality food. Examples of common problems include tardiness in response by staff, insufficient explanations regarding vegetarian options, and understaffing for dining services. These issues frequently result in customer dissatisfaction and may prompt them to seek out alternative options. It's vital to generate consumer loyalty in order to retain clients and avoid losing them to rival establishments. For companies to succeed amidst competitors, they must secure loyalty from consumers that stems from their awareness rather than coercion. To achieve this loyalty, businesses must consider various factors, such as service standards and experiential marketing (Ameen et al., 2021).

One effective marketing method is Experiential Marketing, which focuses on fostering emotional reactions and sparking positive sentiments towards a company's offerings. This is done by imbuing products and services with a blend of intellectual, sensory, and emotional elements that resonate with consumers. The end result is an unforgettable experience that boosts customer satisfaction levels, potentially resulting in repeat business and even new opportunities. In essence, Experiential Marketing recognizes the importance of the emotional bond between customer and product, making it a potent tool for companies seeking a winning marketing strategy.

Mickelsson & Lipkin (2015) contend that customers who display loyalty have a particular fondness for a brand and demonstrate their allegiance by renewing contracts and spreading positive reviews. This phenomenon, defined as a customer's affinity for their preferred product or service, is backed by research conducted by Kotler & Keller (2016). Alternatively, Yusrianti et al. (2017) argue that loyalty stems from a deliberate decision-making process, which leads to habitual purchasing behavior. Despite external influences and marketing tactics, loyal customers remain steadfast in their devotion to their favorite products or services.

Amidst the plethora of choices, a brand's devoted patrons demonstrate commitment, confidence, and allegiance towards its goods, making them loyal. However, managing their loyalty can be tricky, especially since it plays a crucial role in enhancing positive product image. Their unwavering loyalty, despite the alternatives, results in continuous patronage and attachment towards the brand. However, competitors and perception may decrease the profits extracted from their loyalty. Nonetheless, these loyal patrons are priceless assets for companies and might even furnish ideas that improve product quality. The belief in the product and the company's quality trumps price for them. Afthanorhan et al. (2019) define the notion of customer loyalty to encompass.

Experiential marketing has existed for a long time and is not a new concept, according to Lippman. The practice can be observed in well-established markets, where vendors often offer free samples of their products. For instance, a mango seller may offer small pieces of the fruit to attract potential buyers. After trying the sample, interested individuals may start negotiating prices before deciding to purchase the product. If the mango satisfies their taste buds and budget, they are likely to make a purchase. The sight of fresh and ripe mangoes and their pleasing taste greatly influences the potential buyer's decision-making process. This, in turn, leads them to incline towards a purchase that best suits their budget. To entice buyers, the seller follows a clever strategy of offering an extra mango when 10 are bought simultaneously. This traditional custom has been passed down through generations among the Javanese and Madurese populace in Indonesia. Presently, price breaks and discounted rates for larger quantities of certain products are still in vogue. The world of marketing has witnessed a surge in the application of a marketing strategy that involves offering customers additional bonuses upon purchase of certain quantities, and several brands have hopped on this trend. For instance, Indo Mie dishes out a free pack for every five packs bought of the same flavor, Baygon & Hit grants a 20% bonus for higher purchase quantities, Pantene rewards customers who purchase any 200ml pack with an extra 100ml pack of the same product, and Clear offers an additional 50ml bonus pack for each 200ml pack purchased. This technique, which puts a spotlight on brand loyalty and awareness, has proven to be effective in creating a lasting customer base. Using complimentary bonuses or product samples is a well-known tactic to introduce new items to buyers. Brands like Unilever, Nestle, and Sunsilk have implemented this approach with the unveiling of Dove liquid soap, Nescafe Ice, and Sunsilk Hair Nourisher. These samples offer patrons a hands-on and unforgettable encounter. By utilizing experiential marketing, advertisers hope to persuade potential clients to buy the new product and develop brand recognition and perception.

6. CONCLUSION

Customer loyalty is positively affected by both Experiential Marketing and service quality. After conducting a t-test, it was found that graded Experiential Marketing has a significant positive influence on Customer Loyalty in the restaurant Eating Abeng 38, with a tcount greater than ttable. The t-test also showed that partial Quality of Service has a significant positive impact on Customer Loyalty in the same restaurant. Additionally, the outcomes of an F-test revealed that Customer Loyalty in Eating Abeng 38 is impacted by both Experiential Marketing and Service Quality together, with Fhitung values greater than Ftable.

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